

CHARACTERISTICS OF DESIGNER'S SUBCONSCIOUS EVALUATION AS KANSEI PROCESS IN DESIGNING

Toshimasa Yamanaka¹⁾/ Hiroshi Kasai²⁾/ Shino Ida¹⁾

1) Comprehensive Human Sciences, University of Tsukuba/ 2) Denso Corporation
tyam@geijutsu.tsukuba.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

While evaluating designed products, we imagine different feeling between designers and users, or non-design-educated people. This paper introduces how can the difference described. As the research target, we used chairs as familiar product for everybody. AS for the subjective evaluation, semantic differential method was used. For the subconscious measurement, Near Infra-Red Spectroscopy (NIRS), which measures brain function, was used while watching the chair (evaluation) and answering (thinking and expression). As a result, we found specific difference between the evaluation of design educated and non-design educated on the 'Feasibility of Structure' in both measurements. This can illustrates the difference of designer's evaluation as well as the effect of design education.

Keywords: brain function, physiology, affective measurement.

BACKGROUND

'Less is more' (Mies van der Rohe) describes that achieving the maximum effect with the minimum of means. This rule may relate the common tendency of designers that prefer simpler object than expressive product. However, this preference may not always common in non-design-educated people. In other word, designer may have different feeling from users, or non-design-educated people especially when evaluating simplicity or likable of designed object. For example, descriptive form of function, price feeling or symbolic detail design may give comfort feeling to non-designers but designers. Non-designers may not aware the value of simplicity. Even though,

since design regarded to provide better user experience, designers preference should link to the users' mind. In this research, we focused on the difference of feeling in simple object among the designers and non-designers. Then tried to understand the perceptual characteristics of designer as an aspect of designer's Kansei process.

KANSEI AND KANSEI PROCESS

Kansei started to use with Engineering to represent engineering with emotional aspect connecting user and designer. Kansei Engineering represent the special method of analysis that determines human's feeling and product's characteristics. The approach may describe the difference of feeling between designer and non-designer. However the traditional Kansei Engineering depends on subjective description by words or scaled evaluation.

Japanese word kansei is a unique term representing this intuitive mind process (Harada and Lee, 2001). Levy and Yamanaka described kansei as a complex mental process of human beings that involves several emotional feeling such as sensation, perception, and cognition (Levy and Yamanaka, 2006, Beuttel, 2010). This special term, kansei, started to use as a translation of sensibility in Japanese by Akane Nishi, 1857. Then re-applied to the translation of Sinnlichkeit by T. Amano, a philosopher in Japan,

Figure 1. meaning of components of Kansei and Gosei in Japanese.

1935. Sinnlichkeit is intuitive understanding process prior to the Verstand. Japanese character (kanji) can be understood by the comprehension of parts. Kansei in kanji consist with the situation of astonishment + mind and mind + life. Also the Verstand (Gosei, in Japanese) consist with the components of mind + five + describe important things and mind + life (figure 1). It turns out the concept of kansei holds not only 'the sensing ability = sensibility' but 'pre-process of understanding = Sinnlichkeit'. 1980's, Nowadays, kansei become a important word highly related to creative process such as design and planning.

In this research, focusing on the difference between the intuitive evaluation process of designer and non-designer, we would like to introduce the relationship between subjective evaluation and non-subjective or physiological measurement both represents kansei process.

OBJECTIVE

In this research we focused on the design educated people who experienced more than two years of design education in University as the design related group. In the contrary, we set the non-design educated university student as the non-design educated group.

Then we placed research objective to know how the difference comes and developed. The hypothesis is: there will be evaluation gap between design-educated (DE) and non-design educated (NDE) in kansei process.

METHOD AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

As an approach, we used semantic differential method (SD method) to get thinking characteristics through subjective evaluation. At the same time, we measured brain function while seeing and evaluating the design. For the physiological measurement, we used Near Infra-Red Spectroscopy (NIRS). This technology measures the flow volume of oxy-hemoglobin in the frontal cortex of brain that represent the activity of brain. Then after, we compare the result of both measurements.

Figure 2. 50 'famous chairs' for pre-experiment.

PRE-EXPERIMENT

For the pre-experiment, we started to confirm if there are specific difference in kansei process between DE and NDE group observed by subjective expression. For this purpose, we discussed on the target product category. Then agreed with using chair because of its popularity, variation of design and less mechanical or simplicity in function. Then we selected 50 chairs for the research target as familiar product for everybody. Then print the picture of them into same sized cards. We hired five DE and four NDE subjects from University of Tsukuba. We prepared following questionnaire

- 1) which chair do you know?
- 2) which chair do you think simple?
- 3) how did you feel the selected chair as simple?
- 4) which chair do you like?
- 5) what is the reason you liked the chair?

Describing the characteristic of DE, Kang showed the interesting view of relation between the ability of description and evaluation as product (Kang and Yamanaka, 2005). According to Kang, designers tend to find more categories of the product and get higher concentration ratio of favored product into the category. This means DE tend to have higher ability of description and evaluation. In this case, Q 1) represent the descriptive knowledge. And Q 3), 5) represents evaluation of the product. To analyze the relationship between Q1), 3) and 5), we used the number of chairs selected both 1) and 3) as the matching ratio of knowing and simple, 1) and 5) as knowing and like and 3) and 5) as simple and like. Then compared the matching ratio between DE and NDE using AOVA. Even though the poor number of

Figure 3. Selected chair images

panel, we found that there are significant difference. In DE, there we found the tendency of higher relationship of knowing and simple ratio ($p=0.002$) and simple and like ratio ($p=0.03$) compare to NDE. With this result, we found that we can assume that DE shows higher rate on knowing = simple and simple=like. With this result, we tried to know if there is such difference in brain function as well.

EXPERIMENT

Panel and stimulus

Then we planned advanced experiment. For the sample of the evaluation, we referred a design collection of chairs published by Kyusyu Sangyo University, Japan. Then selected appropriate chairs in similar color, material but different structure. To exclude effect of colors and too much ready-made image, we focused on natural colored (beige, light amber) and not-super-modern ones. Then we hired 13 chairs from the collection (figure 2). Usually, subject's reaction can be different in the period of experiment. So, we used two more chairs for training purpose at each set of evaluation. From the limitation of experimental situation, we used digitized image of chairs with all white background.

Images are shown on the 27-inch white frame computer monitor in portrait orientation.

Procedure and Evaluation method

For the subjective evaluation, we applied SD evaluation method. For the sets of adjectives, we conducted to the eight sets of adjectives by conducting subject's comment in pre-experiment (Q2 and Q4) that supposed to be used to evaluate chair design. Then prepared the eight sets of SD pairs as follows.

- 1) simple in form / complex in form
- 2) monolithic / component
- 3) liner shape / curved shape
- 4) simple / complexed
- 5) simple and clean / decorative
- 6) unstable in structure / stable in structure
- 7) eccentric / normal
- 8) reasonable structure / uncertain structure

Then we set up procedure as follows.

1. [watch the target chair]
2. [evaluate score for specific pair of adjectives]
3. [rest]

Then cycled this process up to the numbers of chair x SD combinations that conducted to 120 times of evaluation per subject including two trainings.

While the experiment, we measured subject’s prefrontal cortex that is regarded as the thinking area in brain using 24 channel system of Near Infra-Red Spectrascopy (NIRS, ETG-4000, Hitachi-Medico corp.). The result of NIRS measurement, the amount of oxy-hemoglobin will represent the activity of brain since the brain neuron requires oxygen while processing. For the measuring brain function we compared the process of watching the chair (evaluation) and answering (thinking and expression).

Result and analysis

Result consists with two parts. First, according to the two factors among the experiment, different chair and different user characteristics: DE and NDE, we applied two way ANOVA to determine if there are significant difference in answer according to the

factors. Shown in table 1., chair factor has been significant for all SD scales. This means the subjects’ evaluation was effected by the difference of chair design. This result is quite understandable. However, in relation to the DE and NDE factor, only the [stability in structure] showed significant result while non-significant in interaction. This means the evaluation on the stability in structure becomes different by the design education and the difference is not caused by specific chair but generally applicable difference.

In addition, we applied multiple-discriminant analysis. The result showed the first canonical correlation coefficient showed 0.687 and the [unstable/stable in structure = stability in structure] showed factor loading at 3.737. Comparing to the other independent variables, this is extremely big

table 1. probbility (p) value of two way ANOVA

set of SD	factor1	factor2	interaction
	Chair	DE and NDE	Chair x DEandNDE
1) simple in form / complex in form	<0.001	0.332	0.838
2) monolithic / component	<0.001	0.51	0.14
3) liner shape / curved shape	<0.001	0.913	0.351
4) simple / complexed	<0.001	0.165	0.857
5) simple and clean / decorative	<0.001	0.901	0.221
6) unstable in structure / stable in structure	<0.001	<0.001	0.798
7) eccentric / normal	<0.001	0.32	0.457
8) reasonable structure / uncertain structure	<0.001	0.178	0.937

table 2. factor loading by multiple discriminant analysis

set of SD	1st canonical component
cannonical correlation	0.687
1) simple in form / complex in form	1.27
2) monolithic / component	-0.076
3) liner shape / curved shape	1.462
4) simple / complexed	-0.715
5) simple and clean / decorative	0.581
6) unstable in structure / stable in structure	3.737
7) eccentric / normal	1.197
8) reasonable structure / uncertain structure	1.324

Figure 4. brain function difference between non watching and watching chair image while answering [stability of structure] / DE group. Two channels showed significantly active while watching the chair images.

Figure 5. brain function difference between non watching and watching chair image while answering [stability of structure] / NDE group. No channel showed significantly active while watching the chair images.

figure 5. different functioning brain part in five second of watching the chair images in comparison to the DE and NDE

factor loading. This means, the sense of [stability in structure] works biggest role of difference between design educated and non-design educated students.

Then, we checked the physiological difference in watching and evaluation of the chairs while watching the chair images. In this analysis, we used the analysis software version 1.63 provided by Hitachi medico corp. which uses t-test by subtraction method. In this analysis, we found only the case of answering to the [stability of structure] showed the different result in DE and NDE subjects. Figure 4 shows that there were significant difference between non-watching and watching while preparing to answer the [stability of structure] that means the subject is evaluating in their mind. On the other hand, figure 5 shows the same comparison in NDE subject but shows no significant difference in brain function between watching and non watching the chair image.

In addition to this comparison, we checked the difference between DE and NDE while subjective evaluation. This case, since it is difficult to determine non-evaluation period in experiment, we applied direct comparison between DE and NDE with using averaged data in the evaluation situation. This case, we could see the significant difference in only the right frontal cortex higher in NDE group. (Figure 7)

Figure 7. brain function difference between DE and NDE while subjective evaluation while answering [stability of structure]. Two channels in right frontal cortex functioned significantly different (Higher in NDE) while thinking the answer.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Firstly, in the hypothesis, we expected there could be the significant difference in evaluation on the simplicity but this was not proofed. However, we could confirm both DE and NDE were sensitive to the difference of chairs in evaluation. However only at the evaluation of [stability of structure] showed the difference in both SD evaluation and brain function between DE and NDE. This means that the effect of professional education is developing the different sensitivity of design evaluation but can develops the professional analytical skill such as stability expectation as an fundamental ability of developing potentially new design achievement.

This result shows one aspect of how professional designers skill will be. At the same time, we showed the possibility of brain function and SD evaluation can correlate.

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